

EXTRUSION OF 2124 ALUMINIUM ALLOY POWDERS REINFORCED WITH SiCp

M. Lieblich, G. Caruana, L. Martín*, P. Adeva, G. González-Doncel and M. Torralba
Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Metalúrgicas - CSIC, Avda. de Gregorio del Amo 8, 28040 Madrid, Spain.
* Tecnología Grupo INI, S.A., Pza. Marqués de Salamanca 3, 28006 Madrid, Spain.

ABSTRACT

The effects of extrusion ratio and ram speed on the consolidation of 2124 aluminium powder blended with silicon carbide particles was investigated. The region of extrudability was determined at 480°C. Five quality levels of the extrudates, ranging from good to very bad, are defined. The quality level decreases as deformation and/or deformation rate increase. The maximum deformations and deformation rates achieved to obtaining a composite of good quality are lower than for the unreinforced 2124 alloy.

Keywords: Metal matrix composites, powder metallurgy, extrusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

In general, metal matrix composites (MMC) with ceramic reinforcements combine the high ductility and toughness of metals with the high modulus and tensile strength of ceramics. This combination results in attractive materials for a wide variety of potential applications where low density, high strength and stiffness, and good wear resistance is required (1). The advantages in using aluminium alloys (*e.g.* 2000, 6000 or 7000 series) as the continuous matrix for the preparation of such MMC's has been extensively documented (2,3). Silicon carbide (SiC) is, on the other hand, one of the most successful reinforcement materials for aluminium alloys because of its chemical compatibility with aluminium (up to 500°C) and its high strength and stiffness. Moreover, it confers a high modulus and tensile strength, and good corrosion resistance to the final material (4).

Among the several procedures for the preparation of aluminium matrix composites, the powder metallurgy (PM) route is one of the most extensively used. Through PM, highly homogeneous materials with no reaction between the matrix and the reinforcement are obtained (5). Since the extrusion of powders is usually involved in the final consolidation of these MMC's, it is important to understand the influence of the extrusion variables on the microstructure and properties of the extruded products. This work centres on the influence of extrusion parameters (extrusion ratio and ram speed) on the quality of 2124 aluminium-15% vol. SiC particle composites. The results are compared with those of the unreinforced alloy.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The materials used in this investigation were 2124 atomised aluminium powders (<50µm) as the matrix, and SiC particles (<5µm) as the reinforcement. The aluminium powder and the SiC particles (15 vol.%) were wet-mixed in an ultrasonic bath with acetone as the fluid medium. After

evaporating the acetone in an oven at 50°C, the dry mixture was canned in cylindrical recipients. An Al-Mg-Si alloy was selected for the recipients due to its good extrudability. For comparison, some cans were filled with 2124 unreinforced powders.

The hot extrusion press has a container (42 mm in diameter) which can be heated up to 500°C. Maximum extrusion pressure is about 1600 MPa. Ram speeds varying between 0.4 and 12 mm/s can be selected. For the present work, several extrusions were made at extrusion ratios (R) of 10:1, 14:1, 18:1, 22:1 and 27:1, and ram speeds (v) of 0.8 - 4 mm/s. An extrusion temperature of 480°C was chosen. The consolidated products were bars of 8 to 13 mm in diameter.

Microstructural studies were made by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on both longitudinal and transversal sections of the bars using conventional metallographic procedures.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Polished samples of atomised 2124 particles showed a cellular microstructure, Figure 1. Two types of small particles, corresponding to the CuAl_2 and CuMgAl_2 phases, could be observed by backscattered SEM image on cell boundaries.

Figure 2 is a micrograph of the Al/SiC powder after blending and before consolidation. As can be seen, the distribution of SiC particles (dark areas) is homogeneous except for some small clusters.

Figure 1. Cross section of a 2124 particle (X3500).

Figure 2. Mixture of 2124 / 15 vol.% SiC powders (X180).

Aluminium 2124 alloy has a very low factor of extrudability, less than 15, in comparison with 6063 alloy that is given a dimensionless value of 100 (6). As is known, extrudability is very dependant on extrusion temperature, extrusion ratio (deformation), and extrusion velocity (deformation rate). On the other hand, it is usually admitted that the extrusion ratio of powders must be greater than 9:1 to obtain sound products (7).

Bearing in mind the facts stated above and fixing an extrusion temperature of 480°C, a region of extrusion ratio and velocity (ram speed) where the extruded bars presented full consolidation and good quality was determined. Five levels of quality, ranging from good to very bad, were defined for the extrudates depending upon the degree of cracking of the bars: good quality, fairly good quality, slightly bad quality, bad quality, and very bad quality.

In a first stage, two sets of extrusions were made. In the first one, several extrusions were carried out at an extrusion ratio of 14:1 varying the ram speed from 1.5 to 4 mm/s. In the second one, different extrusion ratios were used at a ram speed of 2 mm/s. As is shown in Table 1, the higher the deformation rate and/or deformation, the worse is the quality of the extruded product.

Table 1. Extrusion ratio (R) and ram speed (v) of the 2124 / 15 vol.% SiCp composite showing the quality of the bars ¹⁾ and the maximum extrusion pressure (MPa).

R / v (mm/s)	0.9	1	1.1	1.2	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4
10:1						● 469	● 484	◇ 499	○ 504	x 584
14:1					● 486	△ 467	◇ 480	○ 518	x 521	x 523
18:1			● 514	△ 504		○ 534				
22:1		● 544		◇ 549		x 554				
27:1	● 544	△ 524				x 568				

1) ● Good quality; △ fairly good quality; ◇ slightly bad quality; ○ bad quality; x very bad quality.

At R=14:1, a fully consolidated bar was obtained at v=1.5mm/s, and at v=2mm/s, full consolidation was obtained at R=10:1. At the extrusion ratio of R=14:1 and ram speed of v=2 mm/s, almost all the bar surface was of good quality, only some sections presented small transversal cracks, Figure 3. At the same extrusion ratio of 14:1 and increasing the velocity to 2.5 mm/s, deeper cracking occurred radially along most part of the bar, Figure 4. This cracking was still superficial in the sense that it affected less than half of bar diameter; the core of the bar did not show any cracking. This type of morphology is known in the literature as fir-tree cracking (8) and is due to a rapid stress accumulation caused either by high deformation or high deformation rate.

Figure 3. Extruded bar of fairly good quality. R=14:1, v=2 mm/s. Bar diameter 11 mm. (*)

Figure 4. Extruded bar of slightly bad quality. R=14:1, v=2.5 mm/s. Bar diameter 11 mm. (*)

As extrusion rate and ratio increased, cracking of the bars was more pronounced. At (R=14:1, v=3mm/s) and (R=18:1, v=2mm/s) fir-tree cracking appeared along all the bars and affected more than half of bar diameters, Figure 5. No cracking was observed in the core of these bars. All this occurred because in the flow pattern developed during extrusion, deformation increases from the

centre towards the bar surface (7). The remaining four extrusions of these two sets, that is ($R=14:1$, $v=3.5$ mm/s), ($R=14:1$, $v=4$ mm/s), ($R=22:1$, $v=2$ mm/s), and ($R=27:1$, $v=2$ mm/s), presented a catastrophic fir-tree cracking, where the consolidated core was so thin that did not confer any rigidity to the bars, Figure 6. It is to be noticed that, whereas the bar had radial cracks, the can presented mainly longitudinal cracks, as shown in Figure 7 for the case of a bar of bad quality. Some radial cracks could also be seen due to local high stresses.

Figure 5. Extruded bar of bad quality. $R=14:1$, $v=3$ mm/s. Bar diameter 11 mm. (*)

Figure 6. Extruded bar of very bad quality. $R=14:1$, $v=3.5$ mm/s. Bar diameter 11 mm. (*)

Figure 7. Extruded bar of bad quality. $R=14:1$, $v=3$ mm/s. Bar diameter 11 mm. (*)

In the second stage, a number of extrusions were carried out to complete the region of extrudability of the 2124/15vol.%SiCp composite. Extrusion ratios of 10:1, 18:1, 22:1 and 27:1 were used. Figure 8 shows the extrudability region that is delimited by the maximum velocity for each extrusion ratio that leads to bars of good quality. This region is for 480°C; at lower extrusion temperatures, the curve would shift to the left.

Some extrusions were carried out with the unreinforced 2124 alloy. Bars of good quality were attained at ($R=14:1$, $v=2$ mm/s), ($R=18:1$, $v=1.2$ mm/s), and ($R=27:1$, $v=1$ mm/s). In view of these results, the curve of Figure 8 would shift to the right, which means that the maximum extrusion velocities required to obtaining good quality bars are higher for the 2124 unreinforced alloy than for the composite.

Figure 8. Extrusion ratio versus ram speed of the 2124 / 15 vol.% SiCp composite.

- Good quality; ▲ fairly good quality; ◇ slightly bad quality; ○ bad quality; x very bad quality.

With concerning the extrusion pressure, it can be deduced from Table 1 that, for the same quality of the bars, the higher the velocity and the extrusion ratio, the higher the pressure; compare for example (R=10:1, v=2mm/s) with (R=10:1, v=2.5mm/s) and (R=14:1, v=2mm/s) with (R=18:1, v=2mm/s). However, when the quality changed from good to fairly good the extrusion pressure decreased slightly; compare for example (R=18:1, v=1.1mm/s) with (R=18:1, v=1.2mm/s).

Finally, a microstructural study was made on the bars of good quality. No remarkable microstructural features were observed between bars obtained with the different extrusion ratios or velocities. In some cases, few small pores were seen at the original aluminium particle boundaries. SiC particles were always homogeneously distributed, whereas precipitates in the matrix were aligned in the extrusion direction, Figure 9. The majority of these precipitates corresponded to the stable Al_2Cu phase. Little precipitation of $CuMgAl_2$ was also detected. Some copper and manganese were detected in the matrix in solid solution.

Figure 9. Microstructure of a longitudinal section of an extruded bar. R=10:1, v=2mm/s.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Rapidly solidified 2124 aluminium powder of less than 50µm was blended with 15 vol.% SiCp of less than 5µm, canned in Al-Mg-Si containers, and extruded. The influence of ram speed and extrusion ratio on the consolidation behaviour of 2124 / 15 vol.% SiCp composite was investigated. The region of extrudability was determined at 480°C. Extrusions were carried out at ram speeds from 0.5 to 4 mm/s and extrusion ratios varying from 10:1 to 27:1.

At high extrusion ratios and/or high ram speeds the extruded bars cracked in a radial manner due to stress accumulation (fir-tree cracking). The quality of the extruded products worsened as deformation and/or deformation rate increased. Low deformations and deformation rates were required for the composite, in comparison with the unreinforced 2124 alloy, to obtain good quality extruded products.

SEM observations of bars of good quality indicated that the distribution of SiCp was homogeneous. The different extrusion ratios and velocities had not any remarkable influence on the microstructure. CuAl₂ and CuMgAl₂ precipitates were aligned in the extrusion direction. Copper and manganese appeared in solid solution in the aluminium matrix. In some cases, small pores could be seen at aluminium particle boundaries.

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(*) Extrusion direction is from left to right.